

Anion Exchange Studies of Ten Metal Ions on Macroporous Resin Using KSCN-DMSO-H₂O Solvent Mixtures

RAM GOPAL VARSHNEY*

Chemistry Department, Janata Vedic College, Baraut-250 611

SHIV NATH TANDON

Chemistry Department, Roorkee University, Roorkee-247 672

and

MOHSIN QURESHI

Chemistry Section, Engineering College, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 001

Manuscript received 10 April 1980, accepted 14 September 1981

The distribution coefficients of ten metal ions have been measured on Dowex macroporous resin, MSA-1, with systems containing various ratios of KSCN, DMSO and H₂O. The concentration of DMSO in a system greatly effects the K_d values. Most metals have decreasing K_d values with increasing amount of DMSO in KSCN solution. Selected separations have been achieved using eluting agents suggested by K_ds.

THE thiocyanate ion is a strong complexing ligand. Similarly DMSO is well known solvent which forms complexes with a large number of metals¹. Thiocyanate, combined with DMSO, opens up a new and interesting possibility. Very little work has been reported on this mixed system. Jauner² seems to have successfully separated Be from numerous metal ions on a cation exchange resin using NH₄SCN-DMSO-H₂O mixtures. Ion exchange studies in NH₄SCN-organic solvent-H₂O mixture were performed on cation³ and anion⁴ exchange resins by Pietrzyk and Kiser. Singh and Tandon⁵ also used NH₄SCN with organic solvents in anion exchange studies of metal ions using acetone, ethanol and methanol. A systematic study of distribution of metal ions in DMSO-aqueous thiocyanate mixed solvent system, however, is lacking. The present paper summarizes our efforts to use such a system for the distribution study of metal ions on an anion exchange resin and to explore some interesting possibilities of separations. As a result, some quantitative separations have been achieved.

Experimental

Apparatus and chemicals: NaI(Tl) well type scintillation counter was used for gamma counting of Cr(51), Mn(54), Co(58), Fe(59), Zn(66), Ag(110m), In(114 m) and Hg(203). Beta counting of Cd and Tl was done on a G. M. counter.

All the reagents and chemicals used were from BDH (Eng.) DMSO was from J. T. Baker Chemical Co., Philipsburg. The strong basic anion exchange macroporous resin, Dowex MSA-1, 20.50 mesh,

Cl⁻ was from Sigma Chemical Co., U.S.A. The radio isotopes of the elements under study were obtained from Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay.

Treatment of resin: The resin was first put in a 5M NaOH solution to convert it into the OH⁻ form. After washing thoroughly to remove the excess of NaOH, it was equilibrated with a 2% aqueous potassium thiocyanate solution for three days. The resin was then washed, air dried and stored in an airtight bottle.

Preparation of the solvents: Pure DMSO was mixed with water and 5M KSCN solution in the following ratios by volume (DMSO: Water: 5M KSCN): 9:0:1, 8:1:1, 6:3:1, 4:5:1, 2:7:1, 0:9:1, 8:0:2, 6:2:2, 4:4:2, 2:6:2, 0:8:2, 6:0:4, 4:2:1, 2:4:4, 0:6:4, 4:0:6, 2:2:6, 0:4:6, 2:0:8, 0:2:8 and 0:0:10.

Measurement of the distribution coefficients: Approximately 200 mg of the dried resin in SCN⁻ form were accurately weighed and taken into a 50 ml corning conical flask. 10 ml of the solvent mixture containing 0.002 meq of the metal ion along with its tracer were then added to it. The flask was tightly stoppered and allowed to stand overnight with intermittent shaking. The supernatant liquid was decanted out and 2 ml of it were used for the radioactive counting. Total counting was then calculated for the whole solution (C_F). A blank was also prepared simultaneously in which the resin was not taken. The radioactive counting of this blank gives the initial concentration of the metal ion in the solution (C_I). The distribution coefficient was

* To whom all correspondence should be made.

then calculated using the formula :

$$K_d = \frac{(C_I - C_F)}{C_F} \times 50 \text{ ml/g}$$

Separation of metal ions : A 4.0 cm column of the resin in the SCN⁻ form was prepared in a micro burette of i.d. 0.8 cm. The elution curves were drawn of different metal ions after loading them on the resin bed and eluting with a suitable solvent mixture at a rate of 10 ml/h. Based on these observations some separations were tried and were found quantitative. The results are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SEPARATION AND ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC MIXTURES OF METAL IONS ON COLUMN PACKED WITH DOWEX MSA-1 RESIN

Ions Separated	Eluents Composition	Amount of metal ion*		% Recovery	
		Volume Added, ml	Found, µg		
Tl(I)-	1M KSCN	24	400.0	400.0	100.0
Fe(III)	0.5M HCl-80% DMSO	36	120.0	124.0	103.3
Tl(I)-	1M KSCN	24	400.0	400.0	100.0
Ag(I)	5M KSCN	18	210.0	208.0	99.0
Tl(I)-	1M KSCN	24	400.0	400.0	100.0
Cd(II)	0.1M EDTA	30	140.0	138.0	98.8
	(0.5M KSCN-90% DMSO)	40	140.0	126.0	90.0
Tl(I)-	1M KSCN	24	400.0	400.0	100.0
Mn(II)	1M KSCN-80% DMSO	28	110.0	106.0	96.4
Tl(I)-	1M KSCN	24	400.0	400.0	100.0
Zn(II)	0.5M KSCN-90% DMSO	30	410.0	420.0	102.5
Tl(I)-	1M KSCN	24	400.0	400.0	100.0
In(III)	0.1M EDTA	22	240.0	235.2	98.0
	(0.5 KSCN-90% DMSO)	38	240.0	168.0	70.0
Mn(II)-	1M KSCN-80% DMSO	28	110.0	105.0	95.5
Fe(III)	0.5M HCl-80% DMSO	36	120.0	123.6	103.0
Mn(II)-	1M KSCN-80% DMSO	28	110.0	105.6	94.0
Co(II)	0.1M KSCN-90% DMSO	22	140.0	137.9	98.5
Mn(II)-	1M KSCN-80% DMSO	28	110.0	105.6	94.0
Cr(III)	0.5M KSCN-90% DMSO	24	100.0	98.6	98.6
Zn(II)-	0.5M KSCN-90% DMSO	30	410.0	421.0	102.8
Fe(III)	0.5M HCl-80% DMSO	36	120.0	124.0	103.3
Zn(II)-	0.5M KSCN-90% DMSO	30	410.0	421.0	102.8
Ag(I)	5M KSCN	20	210.0	207.8	99.0

* Average of atleast two replicates.

Results and Discussion

The result of the study are quite interesting. An increase in the concentration of DMSO in the solvent system containing DMSO, KSCN and H₂O, results in a decrease in the K_d values of the metal ions on anion exchange resin, MSA-1. The behaviour is similar for all the metal ions except Zn(II) and Cd(II) for which the K_d value first increases slightly upto 20% DMSO and then decreases with a further increase in the DMSO concentration. This behaviour of bivalent metals can be understood on the basis of the complex forming ability of these species with metals. The thiocyanate ion produces a series of negatively charged complexes with the metal ion according to the following reaction :

Thus, when the solvent consists of pure thiocyanate (0.5M-5.0M KSCN) negative species are formed with the metal ion and therefore should be greatly

adsorbed on an anion exchange resin. This is experimentally true in these studies. However, the donor properties of DMSO are slightly lower than that of thiocyanate ion⁶. Hence the metal may undergo auto complex formation in DMSO as :

The case of cobalt was discussed by Gutmann⁷ in detail in which he presumed that an octahedral complex Co(NCS)(DMSO)₅⁺ is formed according to the reaction :

It means, therefore, that with an increase of DMSO in the system the concentration of the octahedral positive complex species increases, thus resulting in the low adsorption of the metal ion on an anion exchange resin.

Different metals, when studied in pure KSCN solutions, are found to be adsorbed to different extent on the resin. It may be due to the difference in the stability constants of metal-thiocyanate complex formed in aqueous phase. According to Marcus and Coryell⁸ the stability of metal thiocyanate complex is related with the K_d values on an anion exchange resin as follows :

$$\log D_M^0 = \log D_M - P_M \log \bar{a} = \log K_M - \log \sum \beta_n a^{n-m}$$

where D_M is the experimental K_d, D_M⁰ is the corrected K_d for resin invasion by the supporting electrolyte, a and \bar{a} are the effective ligand activity in aqueous phase and resin, (\bar{a} is measurable as a function of a), P_M is the charge of metal complex predominating in the resin, K_M is constant independent of a, β_n is the effective stability constant referred to the complex species in the aqueous phase and (n-m) is the average charge on the species.

The stability constants of different metal thiocyanates are in the following order⁹ :

On closely studying the K_d values, the same sequence of these metal ions is observed for distribution behaviour which concludes that the greater the stability constants of the metal thiocyanate complexes the greater is its adsorption on an anion exchange resin. This behaviour is obvious.

Separations : Based on the distribution studies of metal ions in the solvent systems containing KSCN, DMSO and H₂O, several separations were tried on the column of Dowex MSA-1 resin. As a result, eleven important and difficult binary separations have been achieved as summarized in Table 1. However, this complexing agent does not seem to be as versatile as is hydrochloric acid for such purposes, but it does offer some additional methods for the separation of metals in DMSO systems.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge support of this work by a grant from the University Grants Commission.

References

1. L. W. REYNOLDS, Progress in Inorganic Chemistry, Volume 12, Interscience, New York, 1970, p 1.
2. G. E. JANAUER and E. O. MADRID, *Micro Chim. Acta*, 1974, 769.
3. J. D. PIETRIZYK and D. L. KISER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1965, 37, 233.
4. J. D. PIETRIZYK and D. L. KISER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1965, 37, 1578.
5. D. SINGH and S. N. TANDON, *Talanta*, 1979, 26, 163.
6. E. A. V. EBSWORTH, A. G. MADDOCK and A. G. SHARPE, *New Path Ways in Inorganic Chemistry*, Chapter 4, Cambridge, At the University Press, 1968, p. 71.
7. E. A. V. EBSWORTH, A. G. MADDOCK and A. G. SHARPE, "New Path Ways in Inorganic Chemistry", Chapter 4, Cambridge, At the University Press, 1968, p 83.
8. Y. MARCUS and C. D. CORYELL, *Bull. Res. Comun. Israel*, 4, 1959, 8, 1.
9. L. G. SILLEN and A. E. MARTELL, Eds., *Stability Constants of Metal Ion Complexes*, The Chemical Society, London, 1964.